

Renewable hydrogen blending into urban natural gas grids with power-to-gas: A techno-economic assessment for Greece

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ABSTRACT

Renewable hydrogen can be produced with Power-to-Gas (PtG) systems, using renewable energy sources (RES), with minimal Greenhouse Gas (GHG) emissions. With this paper, the authors aim to provide clear insights into optimal PtG systems' techno-economic performance, in the case of renewable hydrogen blending into gas grids such as that of the city of Athens. Two different production methods are investigated, namely one in which the investor owns the required energy generation units, and one in which the required energy is procured from independent producers. Seven different underlying parametric scenarios are investigated, reflecting possible future costs developments according to scientific literature. The results show Levelized Costs of produced hydrogen ranging from 2.14 to 5 €/kg. Production through own energy units is currently overall more economical. Energy and electrolysis costs comprise most of the costs, indicating the necessity for considerable price reductions for green hydrogen to become competitive.

1. Introduction

1.1. Background

As of today, hydrogen is used in different sectors of the economy. The most predominant is oil distillation [1]. Hydrogen is essential for ammonia production, reacting with nitrogen in the Haber-Bosch process [2]. Another sector where hydrogen has significant potential is steel production [3]. Other important uses of hydrogen can be found in methanol production [4]. It can be used as an energy carrier, either through direct combustion to produce electricity [5], or through fuel cell conversion [6,7], and to achieve power grid flexibility goals [8,9]. Long-haul trucks, an especially challenging sector to decarbonize, is another candidate use case [10]. Finally, a potential usage of hydrogen is found in district and distributed heating [11], where low-Greenhouse Gas (GHG) hydrogen could either fully replace natural gas (NG) combustion, if the gas infrastructure permits it, or it could be blended with NG, in case there are limitations involved. Hydrogen embrittlement poses a risk to several NG pipelines [12], with EU plans to upgrade gas pipelines to make them hydrogen compatible [13]. The latter has published in June 2023 two Delegated Acts (DA) prescribing what can be considered as renewable fuels of non-biological origin, and a methodology to measure lifecycle GHG emissions of such fuels [14].

Currently, maximum allowed hydrogen admixtures in the NG grids across different EU countries vary significantly. They can range from 0% mol/mol in some EU countries such as Slovakia and Sweden, while reaching up to 20% mol/mol in some sections of the German pipeline system [15,16]. France is currently at 6% mol, Spain at 5% mol, Belgium at 2%, and the Netherlands at 0.5%. However, there are investments underway aiming to upgrade the national NG grids of countries such as Germany and Greece, to be able to carry and handle higher hydrogen admixtures. There are studies, such as [15], indicating the hydrogen compatibility of different gas system components.

With respect to NG usage in Greece, its consumption has been steadily increasing from 2011 to 2021 according to IEA's 2023 report [17]. In 2021, its consumption stood at 6.4 billion N m³ (bcm), up from 4.7 bcm in 2011. When broken down to end consumer type, the biggest share was occupied by NG-fueled electricity generation at 4.4 bcm, followed by the industrial sector at 1.24 bcm, predominantly gray (SMR) hydrogen production at oil distilleries, and the residential and services buildings sectors at 0.6 and 0.2 bcm respectively. The significance of NG for Greece's economy has grown further in recent years, as Greece has been increasingly shifting its electricity production from coal burning to NG. The latter development however, has resulted into increased requirements for NG imports. These rose from roughly

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Nomenclature			
η_{el}	Electrolysis Efficiency	GWP	Global Warming Potential
$C_{Fix.OPEX}$	Fixed Opex (€/MW/year)	IM	Independent Models
C_{inv}	Capital Expenditure (€/MW)	L	Project horizon lifetime (years)
C_{rep}/C_{REPEX}	Replacement Costs (€/MW)	LCOH	Levelized Cost of Hydrogen (€/kg)
$C_{Var.OPEX}$	Variable Opex (€/MWh)	LE	Low End scenarios
$Costs_{ann}$	Annuitized costs (2024 €)	LP	Linear Programming
$E_{g,t}$	Energy of gas g, at hour t (MWh)	NG	Natural Gas
e_g	Volumetric HHV of gas g at STP (MWh/N m ³)	NPV	Net Present Value (2024 €)
H_2	Hydrogen	O&M	Operation & Maintenance costs (€)
HHV_g	High Heating Value (MWh/kg)	OPEX	Operational Expenditure (€)
I_{H_2}	Income from hydrogen sales (€)	PEM/PEMEL	Proton Exchange Membrane Electrolyzer
I_{salv}	Salvage income (€)	PM	Procurement Models
$Income_{ann}$	Annuitized income (2024 €)	PPA	Power Purchase Agreement
L_j	Lifetime of component j (years)	PtG	Power-to-Gas
$M_{g,t}$	Mass of gas g at hour t (kg)	PV	Photovoltaic Panels
O_2	Oxygen	REPEX	Replacement Expenditure (€)
R&D	Research and Development	RES	Renewable Energy Sources
AEL	Alkaline Electrolyzer	ROI	Return on Investment
BoP	Balance of Plant	SMR	Steam-Methane Reforming
CAPEX	Capital Expenditure (€)	SOEC	Solid Oxide Electrolyzer
CCS	Carbon Capture and Storage	STP	Standard Temperature & Pressure
CNG	Condensed Natural Gas	TSO	Transmission System Operator
CRF	Capital Recovery Factor	v/v	volume/volume
d	Investment discount rate		
GHG	Greenhouse Gas Emissions (kg)		

176.4 TJ (0.01 bcm) in 2020, to 642 TJ (0.02 bcm) in 2022 [18]. Most of domestic NG consumption currently concerns energy production purposes [19]. Another factor contributing to this NG imports increase, has been Greece's measures to reduce its energy dependence on Russian NG, partially substituting it with LNG from the US, Algeria, Qatar and Oman [17,19]. Part of these LNG imports have since been exported to neighboring Bulgaria. Greece follows the REPowerEU plan on that matter, which aims to decouple the EU's energy dependence on Russian fossil resources, diversify its energy supply, and save on energy [20]. As of 2023, NG's share in Greece's primary energy mix was at 17.64% [21], while its share in Greece's electricity production mix was 31.69% [21]. These indicators point to the crucial role of NG for both the greek economy, and Greece's energy security. However, other european countries share similar profiles when it comes to NG.

In an effort to meet its obligations within the wider framework of the European Commission's Green Deal [22,23], Greece has published its National Energy and Climate Plan (NCEP) in 2019, setting a roadmap for its effective energy and environmental transition [24]. Among others, it aims at a minimum 82% RES-powered electricity mix, GHG emissions reduction of at least 58.6% of 2005 levels, in line with the EU's target of 55% GHG emissions reduction compared to 1990 levels, and climate neutrality. These should all be achieved by 2050.

In this context of Greece's decarbonization and fossil fuels-phasing out efforts, Power-to-Gas (PtG) systems are a promising tool to bring forth the energy transition, especially within hard to decarbonize sectors. They use water electrolysis, typically from renewable energy sources (RES), to split water into its constituent oxygen and hydrogen. There are three main types of electrolysis, namely Alkaline (AEL), Proton Exchange Membrane (PEM) and Solid Oxide (SOEC), each with different advantages and challenges. There is by now plenty of literature on the comparison between these three latter technologies' efficiencies, such as [25,26], together with projections of PtG underlying components' costs reductions future projections due to learning curve effects and economies of scale [27].

Lastly, similar to other european energy markets, the Greek energy market has undergone significant structural changes over the past decade. With the penetration of independent private RES energy

producers, it has evolved from a single state-owned energy producer and supplier dominated market, to a market with independent producers and suppliers, each holding a smaller share of energy production and supply. In this new energy market landscape, Power Purchase Agreements (PPAs), are a nascent form of energy procurement contract between energy consumers and producers. Their terms are in general subject to negotiations between suppliers and consumers, but their duration usually spans from 5 to 10 years, and the negotiated energy sold has a constant price over the period agreed. Their main advantage over both the Day-Ahead and Intra-Day energy markets, is that they offer hedging against energy prices volatility and uncertainty, enabling both consumers and suppliers to plan their operations in a lower-risk investment environment. These contracts provide an advantage over the Day-Ahead (spot market) and Intra-Day energy markets, which are subject to significant price fluctuations. More information on the different common types of PPAs can be found in [28].

1.2. Motivation and purpose of this study

Given the previously presented challenges, a series of different factors have motivated this study. Most notably:

- Greece currently imports considerable amounts of NG from Azerbaijan, Algeria, Qatar, the US and Russia, either through pipelines or as liquefied NG (LNG), with the accompanying trade balance and other energy dependence and energy security challenges this pertains to [17]. Partial replacement of imported NG with domestically produced green hydrogen could help mitigate these challenges.
- Athens in particular constitutes an important fraction of Greece's aggregate NG consumption, and roughly at ~6–7%, as of 2014–2019 [29,30], rendering it a potential candidate for successful hydrogen blending into its low pressure NG distribution grid, especially during winter, when this consumption is even higher, as a result of building heating requirements, as well as during the summer, when RES availability is comparably high.

- A considerable fraction of Athens GHG emissions currently comes from the combustion of NG. Partially substituting the latter with hydrogen could help Greece achieve its mid-and-long term energy transition and climate neutrality commitments. NG leakage and its environmental impact would be avoided as well.
- The Power Purchase Agreements (PPA) energy market is still rather nascent in Greece, hence research is needed to investigate whether investing in RES generation, or procurement of electrolysis energy from a third producer via PPAs should be preferred, and under which circumstances.
- It is a belief of the authors, that a quantification of PtG systems' performance for this use case is required, in order to compare it with other competing technologies, such as gray and blue hydrogen, as well as RES-powered heat pumps, and obviously NG itself, while reducing the need for pilot plants. Knowledge of accurate figures of Levelized Cost of Hydrogen (LCOH), hydrogen sale prices, system Capital Expenditure (CAPEX), Operational Expenditure (OPEX), Replacement Expenditure (REPEX), investment Net Present Value (NPV), hydrogen penetration into the gases energy mix, as well as GHG emissions under different underlying parameter scenarios affecting system efficiency would be of high importance in particular.

This study aims to provide an in-depth analysis on the techno-economic performance of hydrogen blending into Athens' NG distribution grid. It compares 25-year electrolysis projects, focusing on two different configurations: One in which NPV-optimal investment in an electrolysis unit, hydrogen storage, onshore wind turbines and photovoltaic panels takes place, serving as the electrolysis' energy sources, and one in which the energy required for the AEL electrolysis is procured by RES producers, through PPAs, always aiming to maximize the investment's NPV. The solutions of the resulting Linear Programming (LP) problems are obtained for seven different parametric scenarios, which aim to reflect the dependency of key use case PtG performance indicators on underlying system parameters.

Furthermore, the study aims to aid several different stakeholders' decision making, among others NG and electricity TSOs, NG utility companies, policy makers, as well as energy researchers. In particular, the authors aim to provide a clearer insight into PtG performance for the use case of hydrogen blending into NG distribution grids, and make it comparable to other competing energy and decarbonization solutions.

1.3. Related work

On the topic of lifecycle and techno-economic assessments of PtG applications, plenty of scientific literature has modeled a fixed H₂ output rate. Terlouw et al. examined steady daily hydrogen production rates through PEM electrolysis at five island locations in Europe with high RES potential, deploying three different system configurations; grid-connected, hybrid and off-grid (autonomous) [31]. Their study concluded that there is a clear trade-off between GHG emissions reduction and overall environmental impact on the one hand, and the Levelized Cost of hydrogen (LCOH) of produced hydrogen on the other. Production costs in the range of ~9–16 €/kg of hydrogen were found for the autonomous configurations. However, these results were based on assumptions such as under-optimal design of hydrogen storage sizing, a constant hydrogen demand time series for the whole day, and the deployment of batteries, as well as a compression unit, resulting into overall higher LCOH. Bhandari et al. studied a steady H₂ production resulting from different electrolysis system configurations, grid-connected and off-grid, with AEL and PEMEL [32]. Since grid electricity was occasionally non-renewable however, grid-connected systems could potentially produce the hydrogen in a non-renewable way. The fixed hydrogen output could also potentially lead to sub-optimal results, while not necessarily reflecting a realistic demand

time series. The battery sizing was furthermore assumed to be fixed. However, the high LCOHs should be predominantly attributed to the high specific CAPEX, resulting from the small size of the selected electrolysis, namely at 49 kW for AEL and 62 kW for PEMEL. Such small sizes cannot take advantage of the economies of scale, which usually accompany large-multi-MW electrolysis investments.

Several works have modeled flexible hydrogen supply on the other hand. Sorgulu et al. assessed the supply of both electric and heat demands of 100 houses in the Konya region [33]. Heat was supplied by NG and hydrogen, at a fixed blend rate (20% v/v). Due to the small-scale electrolysis and inflexible hydrogen blending ratio though, LCOHs as high as 52.9 \$/kg were found, whereas their analysis did not address NG leakages as well. Fragiaco et al. studied the production and storage of electrolysis H₂ from wind turbines, solar panels and geothermal energy, in three selected cities in Calabria, Italy [34]. They assessed the supply of a hydrogen fuel cell vehicle fleet and NG grid injections. Lower LCOHs of 6.9 €/kg to 9.85 €/kg were found. Their assumptions included compression of the hydrogen to 350 bar however, necessitating a compression component, together with its electricity-intensive OPEX. Hydrogen injections were delivered at the NG transmission grid as well, resulting to higher hydrogen leakage losses. Furthermore, their modeling assumed constant 5% v/v maximum hydrogen blending ratio.

There is a number of past projects reporting results on PtG-hydrogen injection into the local NG grid. Querton et al. provide a review of such PtG projects [35]. Their result was that at the time of the assessments, none of the projects was economically viable without the external incentive of either H₂ feed-in tariffs or/and some kind of carbon pricing.

Concerning hydrogen compression requirements, according to the report provided by the UK Department of Business in particular [36], compression is only required when H₂ must be injected into high pressure transmission pipelines (85 MPa). For injection into low pressure NG distribution grids (<0.7 MPa), compression is not necessarily needed if the electrolyzer outputs the produced hydrogen under pressures of ~30 bar, or greater than distribution grid pressure in general.

When it comes to Greece's case in particular, there are several PtG and green hydrogen production implementation analyses. Koutsandreas et al. [37] applied multi-criteria decision making modeling (MCDM) for different hydrogen penetration speeds into Greece's power sector. However, their analysis did not incorporate an electricity-NG sector coupling. Karamaneas et al. on the other hand, provided a comparison of different NG penetration speeds into Greece's power energy mix [38]. Their results highlighted the increasing importance of NG as a decarbonization tool, with increasingly ambitious climate policy goals, although PtG technologies penetration into Greece's greater energy sector was not modeled. Nanaki et al. applied a techno-economic analysis comparing the performances of gray, green and Carbon Capture & Storage (CCS) (blue) hydrogen in Greece [39]. Their findings showed that blue hydrogen performed overall more economically than green hydrogen. Their findings were exclusively for oil refinement as use case however. As is evident, there is a lack on accurate techno-economic studies on Greece's NG partial replacement with green hydrogen.

Another important topic on successful blending, is natural gas infrastructure compatibility with hydrogen. In their NREL report on natural gas infrastructure hydrogen compatibility, Topolski et al. provide a detailed and extensive overview of all the key challenges which need to be overcome to upgrade existing gas grids to support hydrogen transmission, distribution and utilization [40]. Hydrogen integration in natural gas grids involves difficulties stemming from the differences in physical and thermodynamic properties of natural gas and hydrogen, typically mass density, pressure, heating value, Wobbe index, flammability. Hydrogen can also lead to steel embrittlement and fracture in gas pipelines, valves and other infrastructure. Topolski provides extensive literature on steel gas transmission systems' embrittlement.

Since hydrogen's molecule is smaller than that of methane or other hydrocarbons, it can more easily leak, for instance at gas valves. Hydrogen has a lower energy density than natural gas, meaning that a higher volume of gas mix would be needed to satisfy the same energy demand, accompanied by higher gas velocity. When it comes to distribution grids, these can be more resilient to negative corrosive hydrogen effects, due to lower pressure requirements, and the fact that pipelines are often composed of polyethylene instead of steel, which is more hydrogen-resilient. Athens' distribution grid in particular is comprised of a combination of the two types of pipelines [41]. While studying blending hydrogen in polymethylene pipelines, Haeseldonckx et al. found that although hydrogen leakage from pipe walls was 5 times higher than that of methane, total hydrogen leakage was negligible, amounting to 0.0005%–0.001% of total volume transported [42].

While many of current natural gas grid end uses can combust a mix of hydrogen and natural gas, there may be end uses which require either pure hydrogen, or almost pure natural gas. A typical example of the former is PEM Fuel Cells, whereas an example of the latter is CNG cars. Key technologies for hydrogen separation can be found in [43].

Cerniauskas et al. compared four different alternative reassignment strategies of hydrogen transmission methods [44]. Firstly, the addition of inhibitors such as C₂, SO₂, CO to the gas mix, which will reduce hydrogen-pipeline interaction; the coating of pipelines, the insertion of pipelines within exiting pipelines, and lastly simply using the pipelines without any modification, but with enhanced maintenance, in order to monitor and optimally manage material degradation. For smaller diameter pipelines, such as typically those of low pressure distribution grids, the deployment of the inhibitors results in the same cost reductions as the “no modifications” strategy. Their outcome was that such type of reassignment could be 20%–60% cheaper compared to the installation of new hydrogen compatible pipelines, for the case of Germany. In the cheapest “no modification” alternative, it was assumed that only investment in new hydrogen-compatible compressors and gas regulation pressure stations will be required. Cost function were also derived for the four technologies.

1.4. Contribution

Several gaps in preceding scientific literature are hence attempted to be filled with this study. In particular:

- Hydrogen supply quantity was assumed constant in regional studies such as [32,45]. The authors attempt a first regional techno-economic study on the decarbonization of the greater Athens region's NG consumption through PtG systems, based on real NG consumption data. However, the results can be generalized to incorporate regions with similar RES, climatic and NG consumption profiles, among others those of the greater Mediterranean or Balkans regions.
- In contrast to preceding literature, maximum allowed blends of up to 100% v/v in hydrogen are studied. The hourly blend ratios are further optimized, instead of being fixed (e.g. [33,34]), aiming at LCOH and system costs minimization.
- Unlike several PtG literature up to now (e.g. [31–33,39,46]), the models deployed in this study optimize electrolysis, onshore wind turbines, and photovoltaic panels installation sizes simultaneously, instead of only a selection thereof at a time.
- Economies of scale were not taken advantage of in several PtG techno-economic studies, such as [33,34], leading into overall expensive green H₂. This study incorporates them, assuming multi-MW electrolysis takes place where applicable, typically when H₂ demand allows it.
- Hydrogen storage over- or -undersizing is a common drawback of several scientific literature works, leading to overall high system costs [31,33]. This is furthermore eliminated in the deployed models, since they can optimize this variable with respect to investment NPV as well.

- Since this is a blending into the low-pressure NG distribution grid, a compression unit could also be spared, without any system efficiencies losses, reducing overall system costs. Due to different use case requirements, several studies have included expensive compression units, such as in [31,34].
- The replacement, whenever needed, of the system components, typically electrolyzer stacks and hydrogen containers, as well as their salvage income at the end of the project lifetime are also taken into account, resulting into more accurate system costs results. Works such as [32,34,46] do not address PtG components' replacement costs.
- Lastly, NG leakage, its avoidance through its partial replacement through hydrogen, and the accompanying savings in GHG emissions are also taken into consideration, whereas this is not accounted for in all previously presented literature.

The study is structured as follows. In Section 1, we presented the background of PtG systems emphasizing on the Greek context alongside a description of related work and contributions of our study. Section 2 presents our methodology, where the development of the two models and the different parametric scenarios investigated are defined and discussed alongside data curation, selection, analysis, and most importantly the mathematical formulation of the resulting linear programming (LP) problem. Subsequently, in Section 3, we graphically present and discuss the results of the optimization algorithms. Finally, Section 4 wraps up the document with concluding remarks, limitations, and future perspectives.

2. Methodology

2.1. Models description

Two model families are assessed and compared to each other. In the first model family, investments in onshore wind turbines and solar panels are considered, which are connected to the power grid for a certain fee paid to the Transmission System Operator (TSO). Then, their generated energy is assumed to supply the TSO-connected AEL electrolysis site. We refer to this model family as “*Independent Models*” (IM). In the second model family, instead of investing in RES installations which come with a significantly high initial CAPEX, the required for the electrolysis energy is procured from independent RES energy producers, via PPAs, at a fixed price per procured MWh. We refer to this model family as “*Procurement Models*” (PM).

Hydrogen produced at the electrolysis site can either be stored in hydrogen containers for future use or injected directly into the gas distribution grid. The extent of injection can range from partial to complete, depending on system requirements. Upon injection into the gas grid, the hydrogen is assumed to be sold at a fixed price per kg. Fig. 1 shows these PtG systems' configuration. The models are built with PyPSA library [47], which uses Linopy to model the LP problem's objective function and constraints, and the GLPK solver to solve the resulting LP problem [48,49].

Time series of hourly wind turbines capacity factors, PV capacity factors, as well as NG consumption in thermal units (MWh measured with the HHVs of NG and H₂) were fed into the optimization models. Yearly variations in RES capacity factors are primarily driven by weather fluctuations, with technological advancements contributing marginally over time. Similarly, yearly variations in NG consumption are influenced primarily by weather-related heating and cooling demands. As such, all three time series fed into the models concerned $N = 3$ years of hourly data, in order to both incorporate yearly weather variability, while simultaneously maintaining reasonable computing time requirements.

Fig. 1. Power-to-gas models configuration.

2.2. Parameter scenarios

The main drivers of electrolysis costs are energy prices, RES generation CAPEX, electrolyzer CAPEX, electrolysis efficiency, and gas pipeline and network compatibility with hydrogen. Scientific literature supports reductions in electrolysis costs due to technological learning curve effects, and onshore wind and PV panels technologies progress, as a result of ongoing Research and Development (R&D) [50–52]. Also, the same literature supports further reductions of electrolysis costs, due to economies of scale taking place in the future, and as manufacturing of electrolysis and RES generation becomes more standardized and modules are more mass produced. As a result, seven parametric scenarios are investigated: the first, referred to as “Main” scenario, reflects current 2024 electrolysis, RES generation, and H₂ storage costs, as well as 10% maximum allowed H₂ volumetric blends. Another six parametric scenarios, referred to as “low-end scenarios”, named as “LE1, LE2, ..., LE6”, reflect the above possible future PtG costs reductions and gas grid hydrogen compatibility improvements. Fig. 2 graphically represents the models’ parameter inputs, as well as onshore wind turbines and photovoltaic (PV) panels capacity factors, and NG energy consumption time series used as inputs for the models.

2.3. Energy demand

The thermal energy data examined in this study were obtained from DESFA. They refer to the hourly time series of NG thermal energy, assuming the High Heating Value (HHV) of NG deliveries, supplied to the national NG grid’s exit point of the city of Athens [53]. The term “exit point” means the point where the transmission system delivers gas to a local distribution system, in our case that of Athens. While the data obtained from DESFA span over the period 01/09/2014 at 8:00 to 01/08/2018 at 07:00, not all data was used, due to model solving time complexity constraints. The data fed to the models span over the period 01/09/2014 at 8:00 to 01/09/2017 at 07:00, and reflect the consumption of NG of the city of Athens during this period, namely three years of consumption. A yearly average consumption of ~3.1 TWh was found. A yearly average consumption relative standard deviation of 4.4% was found for the years 2015–17, indicating small yearly NG consumption deviations, likely related to weather variability. Fig. 3 illustrates the average hourly consumption of NG for Athens, for every month, for years 2015–2017. It shows that winter months expectedly require higher deliveries of NG energy.

Another dataset obtained from DESFA, concerned the daily HHV time series of NG deliveries, as measured at the same site [29]. NG is a gaseous mixture primarily comprising methane, ethane, butane, and propane, with varying concentrations that slightly impact its HHV. A standard deviation of NG’s HHV of ~4.7% of the mean value was found for the grid’s exit point of Athens for the time series used. The average HHV of the time series was assumed for the models, equal to 14.85 kWh/kg of NG.

At that site, the NG is delivered to the NG distribution network, under a pressure of 6 bar, at ambient temperature. The aim is to optimally

Fig. 2. Power-to-gas models setup. Cylinders depict the data fed to the models. Colored modules depict system components. Colored arrows depict energy flows.

replace this consumption with green hydrogen. Fig. 4 shows the effect which hydrogen blending has on gas mixture mass and volumetric HHVs, as a result of the two gases differences in HHV, energy density and mass density properties. An assumed demand constraint in the models is that at every hour of the simulations, that latter mixture of NG and hydrogen quantities must carry as much energy as it is required by the NG energy demand during that hour, as obtained by the Greek NG TSO (DESFA) data set [30]. In other words:

$$D_t = E_{total,t} = E_{NG,t} + E_{H_2,t} \quad t = 1, 2, \dots, T \tag{1.0}$$

where D_t is the energy demand at hour t , and T is the last time step of the optimization process, considered as the last hour of a 3-year period, or $T = 3 \cdot 365 \cdot 24 = 26,280$.

Fig. 3. Average hourly NG consumption for Athens (2015–2017). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 4. Effect of hydrogen blending on mixture mass and volumetric HHVs.

2.4. System components

2.4.1. Wind turbines and solar panels

Simulations of hourly energy output of wind turbines and photovoltaic panels were obtained from the open-source project Renewables.ninja [54], based on the works of S. Pfenninger and I. Staffel [55, 56]. The weather data utilized in the simulated RES output time series come from NASA’s MERRA project, and CM-SAF’s SARAH dataset. The energy output data for both onshore wind turbines and PV panels represent the maximum achievable generation outputs at every simulated time-slot, but the actual generators’ outputs could naturally be lower in the models’ solutions, if this leads to better LP solutions. This can also happen if the generators’ energy output is about to exceed the electrolysis unit’s nominal capacity. The installations of the renewable generators were assumed to be located at suitably selected sites within the Attica region, Greece. Nevertheless, this is not necessary, due to their connectivity with the TSO in the developed models. Table 1 summarizes the generators’ specifications for all considered parametric scenarios accompanied by their respective sources.

2.4.2. Electrolysis unit

An AEL unit is deployed in the models, as this type of electrolysis is still overall more economic than PEMEL, although literature supports that their costs could equalize after 2030. The electrolyzers’ stacks are

assumed to be replaced at the end of its lifetime, namely twice during the PtG project’s 25-year lifetime, and the entire electrolysis unit is assumed to be sold at the end of the project’s lifetime. Table 2 contains the specifications of the AEL unit deployed in the experiments for all parametric scenarios accompanied by their respective sources.

2.4.3. Hydrogen storage unit

A Type I hydrogen storage container facility is assumed in the models, serving as an energy buffer. Type I hydrogen storage containers are the cheapest option of large-scale hydrogen storage, deployed typically in industry when there are no strict space constraints. Type I containers are typically made of steel or aluminum alloy, and can store hydrogen at low pressures, up to 30 bar. Since the electrolyzer used outputs hydrogen at 30 bar, this means that no investment in compressors is needed to store the hydrogen into the containers. More information on Type I hydrogen storage can be found in [57]. Table 3 lists the specifications of the storage unit for all parametric scenarios accompanied by their respective sources.

2.4.4. Other model parameters

The electrolysis site and RES generation sites are assumed to be connected with each other through electricity grid TSO, and a yearly fee is paid for this service to the TSO. Furthermore, a tax for the consumed electricity is paid. About 1% of hydrogen energy was assumed in the models to be lost during the distribution to the end consumers due to leakage, although there are very limited sources for this value to date, as a result of limited number of pilot projects measuring hydrogen leakage. Common leakage patterns as those of NG leakages were therefore assumed in the models. An additional 1% energy loss was assumed for hydrogen storage, with a further 1% loss during buffer discharge, whenever H₂ is retrieved from it. A uniform constant NG HHV and molar mass were assumed in the models, equal to the average values of the respective time series of the data set provided by DESFA. A conservative estimate of 1% total mass and energy loss for NG due to supply chain leakages was assumed, based on existing literature, although this figure could be higher in reality. Table 4 sums up these model parameters accompanied by their respective sources.

2.5. Model formulations

2.5.1. Objective function

In both model families, the LP objective function was the annuitized NPV cash flows of the investments made, following a similar reasoning as in [31]:

$$Obj. : \max \quad Income_{ann} - Costs_{ann} \tag{1.1}$$

$$Income_{ann} = I_{H_2,ann} + I_{salv,ann} \tag{1.2}$$

$$Costs_{ann} = C_{inv,ann} + C_{Fix.OPEX} + C_{Var.OPEX} + C_{REPEX,ann} \tag{1.3}$$

An explanation for each term follows.

Income comes in the form of:

- selling the produced hydrogen at a fixed price.
- selling any of the system components at the end of the project horizon (salvage income).

The annuitized income from selling the produced hydrogen is then:

$$I_{H_2,ann} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{t=1}^T M_{H_2,t} \cdot p_{H_2} \tag{2.1}$$

where p_{H_2} is the hydrogen sale price, $M_{H_2,t}$ the mass of hydrogen sold at hour t , and $T = 24 \cdot 365 \cdot N = 8760 \cdot N = 26,280$, where N is the number of years of onshore wind, PV, and NG consumption data used

Table 1
Wind turbines and PV panels specifications per parametric scenario.

Wind turbines	Parametric scenario							Units	Sources
	Main	LE1	LE2	LE3	LE4	LE5	LE6		
Specific CAPEX	1 104 000	1 048 800	993 600	883 200	772 800	772 800	717 600	€/MW	[58–60]
Fixed O&M costs	27 400	26 030	24 660	20 550	17 810	17 810	17 810	€/MW/year	[31,58,61]
PPA price	53	50.35	47.7	39.75	37.1	37.1	37.1	€/MWh	[34,46,62]
Lifetime				27				years	[58]
Replacement costs				70% of CAPEX					[31]
Salvage income				70% of CAPEX					[31]
PV panels									
Specific CAPEX	680 000	646 000	612 000	544 000	476 000	476 000	442 000	€/MW	[32,58,63–65]
Fixed O&M costs	15 250	14 487.5	13 725	11 437.5	10 675	10 675	10 675	€/MW/year	[63,64,66]
PPA price	31.8	30.21	28.62	23.85	22.26	22.26	20.67	€/MWh	[34,62]
Lifetime				30				years	[58,63]
Replacement costs				70% of CAPEX					[31]
Salvage income				70% of CAPEX					[31]

Table 2
AEL specifications per parametric scenario.

	Parametric scenario							Units	Sources
	Main	LE1	LE2	LE3	LE4	LE5	LE6		
Specific CAPEX	924 000	877 800	831 600	600 600	554 400	554 400	554 400	€/MW	[27,32,36,67,68]
Fixed O&M costs	18 480	17 556	16 632	12 012	11 088	11 088	11 088	€/MW/year	[31,34,69]
Variable O&M costs	1.33	1.33	1.33	1.33	1.33	1.33	1.33	€/MWh (el.)	[31,34,69]
Water costs				1.33				€/MWh(el.)	Based on [70]
Efficiency (HHV)	75.6	79	82	85	85	85	85	%	[25,32,65,69,71,72]
BoP specific CAPEX				2% of electrolyzer sp.CAPEX					[69], own assumptions
BoP fixed OPEX				10% of electrolyzer fix.OPEX					[69], own assumptions
BoP el. consumption				1% of electrolyzer consump.					[69], own assumptions
Stack lifetime				9				years	[27,32,36,68,69,73]
Replacement costs				30% of CAPEX					[31]
Salvage income				30% of CAPEX					[31]
Oper. Temperature				50–80				°C	[26,73]
Pressure				30				bar	[26,32,34,36,73,74]
CAPEX forecasts									[27,35,36]
Water requirement				2				L/N m ³	[32]
Hydrogen purity				Assumed 100 (99.5–99.9)				%	[32]
Max. H ₂ blend	10	20	30	50	80	90	100	% v/v in mixture	Own assumptions

Table 3
Hydrogen storage containers specifications.

	Parametric scenario							Units	Sources
	Main	LE1	LE2	LE3	LE4	LE5	LE6		
Specific CAPEX	14 500	13 775	13 050	11 600	10 150	10 150	10 150	€/MWh of H ₂	[31,34,75,76]
Fixed O&M	290	275.5	261	232	203	203	203	€/MWh of H ₂ /year	[31,34,75]
Variable O&M				Negligible					[36]
Pressure				≤30				bar	[31,75]
Lifetime				20				years	[31]
Replacement costs				75% of CAPEX					[31]
Salvage costs				75% of CAPEX					[31]
Charging losses				1% of H ₂ energy being stored					Own assumption
Discharge losses				1% of H ₂ energy being retrieved					Own assumption

Table 4
Other models parameters.

	Value	Units	Sources
Project lifetime	25	years	Own assumption
Energy tax	6	% of procured energy price	[77]
TSO fee	37 464	€/MW electrolysis/year	[77]
Discount rate	7	%	Own assumption
Hydrogen transmission leakage	1	% of hydrogen energy transferred	Own assumption
Nat. gas transmission leakage	1	% of nat.gas energy transferred	[78], own assumptions
Hydrogen GWP	Negligible	g CO ₂ eq./g H ₂	Own assumption
CO ₂ GWP	1	g CO ₂ eq./g CO ₂	Per definition
Natural gas GWP	28	g CO ₂ eq./g NG	[79]
Hydrogen HHV	39.38	kWh/kg	[80]
Natural gas average HHV	14.85	kWh/kg	DEPA data set
Hydrogen energy density (HHV @STP)	12.7	MJ/N m ³	[80]
Natural gas energy density (HHV@STP)	40.6	MJ/N m ³	[80]
Hydrogen molar mass	2.01568	g/mol	
Natural gas average molar mass	17.47	g/mol	DESFA data set

in the LP problem. For the results of this study, $N = 3$ was chosen. The mass, thermal energy of hydrogen, and the electric energy required to produce that mass of hydrogen are further connected by:

$$M_{H_2,t} = \frac{E_{H_2,t}}{HHV_{H_2}} = \frac{\eta_{el} \cdot E_{electric,t}}{HHV_{H_2}} \quad (2.2)$$

where η_{el} is the efficiency of the electrolysis.

When system components, namely the electrolysis unit and the hydrogen storage unit are sold at the end of the project lifetime, they incur salvage income, given by:

$$I_{salv,ann} = CRF(d, L) \sum_{j=1}^J \frac{I_{salv,j}}{(1+d)^L} \quad (2.3)$$

Following the calculations in [81], $I_{salv,j}$ is the salvage income of component j , which is given by

$$I_{salv,j} = C_{rep,j} \frac{L_{rem,j}}{L_j} \quad (2.4.1)$$

$$L_{rem,j} = L_j - (L - L_{rep,j}) \quad (2.4.2)$$

$$L_{rep,j} = L_j \cdot INT\left[\frac{L}{L_j}\right] \quad (2.4.3)$$

where $INT[a]$ is the integer part of a , and $C_{rep,j}$ is the replacement cost of component j .

In Eq. (2.3), d is the discount rate and L is the project lifetime. L_j is the lifetime of component j . $CRF(d, L)$ is a multiplier called Capital Recovery Factor. It is given by:

$$CRF(d, L) = \frac{d(1+d)^L}{(1+d)^L - 1} \quad (2.5)$$

In the equation above, d is the discount rate, and L is the project horizon lifetime. An in-depth explanation of the meaning of the CRF can be found in [81].

Costs come in the form of:

- Investment (CAPEX) costs for all system components procurement and their installations.
- Fixed OPEX, for all system components, most notably maintenance, insurance, workers-related costs, and TSO fees.
- Variable OPEX for all system components, typically PPA costs in PM, energy taxes and electrolysis water-related costs.
- Replacement (REPEX) costs of system components, namely the electrolyzer stacks and hydrogen containers, at the end of their lifetimes.

In order to make the payments of the investment and replacement costs of the $j = 1, 2, \dots, J$ system components annuitized, the following calculations are used:

$$C_{inv,ann} = CRF(d, L) \sum_{j=1}^J C_{inv,j} \quad (3.1)$$

and

$$C_{Rep,ann} = CRF(d, L) \sum_{j=1}^J \frac{C_{Rep,j}}{(1+d)^{L_j}} \quad (3.2)$$

Fixed OPEX is assumed to be paid once a year, while variable OPEX in an hourly basis:

$$C_{Fix.OPEX} = \sum_{j=1}^J C_{Fix.OPEX,j} \quad (3.3)$$

$$C_{Var.OPEX} = \sum_{j=1}^J \sum_{t=1}^T C_{Var.OPEX,j,t} \quad (3.4)$$

2.5.2. Hydrogen blending constraint

As a result of partial NG grid incompatibility with hydrogen, a maximum allowed volumetric ratio, as well as the energy ratio of hydrogen and NG blend in the gases mix are defined as below:

$$\lambda_{max} = \frac{V_{H_2}}{V_{total}} \quad (4.1)$$

$$r_{max} = \frac{E_{H_2}}{E_{ng}} \quad (4.2)$$

where $V_{total} = V_{H_2} + V_{ng}$, $E_{total} = E_{H_2} + E_{ng}$. Since most models' LP decision variables in PyPSA need to be expressed in energy units, the maximum hydrogen blending constraint must be written in such terms. If we denote the hydrogen volumetric blending as λ , and the hydrogen–NG energy ratio in the blend as r respectively, and assuming ideal gas behavior for both NG and H_2 , then it follows that:

$$r = \gamma \frac{\lambda}{1 - \lambda} \quad (4.3)$$

$$\gamma = \frac{e_{H_2}}{e_{ng}} \quad (4.4)$$

where e_{H_2}, e_{ng} are the volumetric energy densities of hydrogen and NG respectively. Then, r_{max} can be computed by (4.3), for $\lambda = \lambda_{max}$. Then the maximum allowed hydrogen blending constraint is written as:

$$E_{H_2,t} \leq r_{max} \cdot E_{ng,t} \quad t = 1, 2, \dots, T \quad (4.5)$$

2.5.3. Levelized cost of hydrogen

The resulting (LCOH) can then be computed as:

$$LCOH = \frac{\text{Project Levelized Costs}}{\text{Levelized } H_2 \text{ production}} \quad (5.1)$$

$$\text{Project Levelized Costs} = \sum_{y=1}^L \frac{\text{Costs}_{ann}}{(1+d)^y} \quad (5.2)$$

$$\text{Levelized } H_2 \text{ production} = \sum_{y=1}^L \frac{M_{H_2,ann}}{(1+d)^y} \quad (5.3)$$

$$M_{H_2,ann} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{t=1}^T M_{H_2,t} \quad (5.4)$$

2.5.4. GHG emissions

GHG emissions happen for two reasons in the models:

- Combustion of NG consumed.
- Leakage of NG.

It is assumed that hydrogen GHG emissions are negligible compared to NG GHG emissions. Then, the GHG emissions are calculated as:

$$GHG_{total} = GHG_{comb} + GHG_{leak} \quad (6.1)$$

$$GHG_{comb} = \frac{E_{ng}}{HHV_{ng}} \cdot 2.75 \cdot g_{CO_2} \quad (6.2)$$

$$GHG_{leak} = M_{leak,ng} \cdot g_{ng}$$

or:

$$GHG_{leak} = \frac{l}{1-l} \cdot \frac{E_{ng}}{HHV_{ng}} \cdot g_{ng} \quad (6.3)$$

$$l = \frac{E_{ng,leaked}}{E_{ng,total}} \quad (6.4)$$

where l is the leakage as a fraction of total NG energy, and coefficients g_{CO_2}, g_{ng} are the GWPs of CO_2 and NG respectively. The 2.75 multiplier in (6.2) comes from the fact that perfect combustion of 1 kg of NG results into ~ 2.75 kg of CO_2 eq. emissions. In the models, it was assumed that g_{ng} is equal to the GWP of methane, since this is by far the most abundant constituent of NG.

Fig. 5. Optimal onshore wind turbines installation per scenario and hydrogen price.

3. Results

Figs. 5–15 contain the experiments results. Concerning technical aspects of the experiments, Figs. 5, 6 and 7 illustrate the optimal installed capacities of onshore wind turbines, PV panels, and electrolysis size as functions of the hydrogen sale price and parametric scenario, for IM and PM respectively. Fig. 8 depicts the NPV-optimally installed hydrogen storage capacities for the same variables, in tons of hydrogen. Fig. 9 shows the average yearly hydrogen production in tons. Fig. 10 shows the Levelized Cost of hydrogen by scenario and hydrogen price for the two model families. Fig. 11 depicts the GHG emissions of the experiments, as fractions of the “baseline” system configuration, in which there is absolutely no hydrogen blending, and all energy is supplied by NG, in other words, the current 2024 situation. Fig. 12 shows the average hydrogen share in the total gas energy mix over the entire simulation’s duration, as a fraction of the total energy supplied. The lines connecting the experiments’ results points on the graphs are intrapolations of the respective simulated statistics. Average annual GHG emissions of the baseline scenario were calculated at 601.62 kt of CO₂ equivalent, as a result of both NG combustion, and NG leakage, for the entirety of the NG journey from extraction to end-use consumption point. The NG and hydrogen blends are assumed to be fully combusted.

Regarding the economic results of the experiments, Fig. 13 depicts the total costs breakdown for the two model families, for the specific case of scenario LE3, when hydrogen is sold at 3.5 €/kg. The costs breakdown pattern appearing remains is in fact representative for all scenarios and hydrogen prices, with minor differentiations. Lastly, Figs. 14 and 15 show the investments’ Net Present Values and Return on Investment rates, for the two model families.

3.1. Effect of H₂ sale price and parametric scenario

Increasing the hydrogen sale price, expectedly increases all system components’ NPV-optimally installed sizes, since more revenue can be generated by selling greater quantities of hydrogen, thus also spent in expanding the components’ sizes. These components are namely both onshore wind turbines and PV panels, as well as electrolysis and hydrogen storage (Figs. 5–8). This eventually leads into greater annual green H₂ production and higher GHG emissions savings as well (Figs. 9, 11). There exists hence a trade-off between hydrogen sale price on the one hand, and gas grid de-carbonization on the other, in accordance to the findings of [31]. Both investment NPV and ROI increase with hydrogen sale price too, as expected and shown in Figs. 14 and 15.

A similar pattern occurs while moving from the Main and low LE scenarios, to LE6. Lower PtG components’ specific costs and higher maximum allowed hydrogen volumetric blending ratios expectedly

make it possible for more energy consumption to be supplied with hydrogen at any point in time, whilst also more cost-effectively. Relaxing the maximum hydrogen blending constraint also leads to LP problem solutions with lower H₂ price thresholds. In other words, into investments which allow lower hydrogen sale prices and higher GHG savings, without sacrificing NPV positivity. To illustrate an example, GHG savings hardly increase, no matter how expensively the investor sells a kg of H₂. On the opposite side, just an increase from 2.14 to 2.5 €/kg moves GHG emissions from 89% to just over 70% of the baseline scenario. For every parametric scenario, the solution with the lowest H₂ sale price appearing in the figures was experimentally chosen by trial and error to be very near that threshold. For instance, no feasible LP solutions were found for the Main scenario, for H₂ price less than ~4 €/kg. For LE6 on the other hand, that threshold was found to be around 2.14 €/kg, as the diagrams show. The drop of the threshold hydrogen sale price from the Main, all the way to LE6 scenario is expected, since hydrogen production becomes more and more cost-effective when moving in this direction, as a result of decreasing RES generation, electrolysis, storage and PPA costs, as well as increasing electrolysis efficiency.

However, as can be seen in Fig. 9, H₂ production quantity also depends on the price at which the investor sells it. As a result, the threshold H₂-feasible LP prices lead to generally low produced quantities, and higher prices are required for greater H₂ production, as well as penetration into the gases energy mix, and GHG emissions savings among others (Figs. 12, 11). As a result, de-carbonization of the NG grid comes at the price of more expensive H₂. The driving factor behind this outcome, is that “cheaper” to decarbonize hours are supplied with H₂ first under Simplex algorithm, and as such, de-carbonization becomes harder with increasing investment revenues, or equivalently, H₂ sale prices. In other words, Simplex prioritizes which hours to supply with hydrogen, according to the income they bring when selling the hydrogen. Thus, hours with plenty of RES resources and high energy demand will always be supplied first. Which then means that in most of the experiments performed, those hours will always be supplied with hydrogen, if not even with the same quantity. But in experiments where more hydrogen can be generated as a result of more financial resources available to buy RES generation capacity, in other words, higher hydrogen sale price, also less profitable hours will ultimately be able to be supplied with hydrogen, albeit less cost-effectively than the supply of the more profitable demand hours. This is the reason why LCOH slowly increases with hydrogen sale price, and why hydrogen production volume as a function of both hydrogen price and LCOH, is an increasing function.

Another crucial observation is the rate of change of all important variables’ LP optimal values with respect to the sale price, per

Fig. 6. Optimal PV installation per scenario and hydrogen price.

Fig. 7. Optimal electrolysis installation per scenario and hydrogen price.

Fig. 8. Optimal hydrogen storage capacity in tons.

parametric scenario. Namely the rates:

$$R_S = \left. \frac{dQ}{dp} \right|_S \quad (7)$$

where Q is the optimal values of wind turbines, PVs, electrolysis, storage sizes, LCOH, H_2 yearly production, GHG emissions as fraction of baseline system, and average hydrogen energy share in the gases mix, p is the sale price, and S denotes the parametric scenario: $S = Main, LE1, \dots, LE6$. As can be seen in the figures, which are plotted

in logarithmic y -axis, this rate absolutely increases when we move to higher parametric scenarios. This means that the same change in hydrogen price leads to bigger changes in Q , for higher parametric scenarios. In other words, all quantities Q become increasingly more sensitive to the sale price p , when moving to higher parametric scenarios. The curvature is also greater towards the smaller LP-feasible prices, denoting for example for IM LE4 bigger GHG savings when selling at 3 €/kg instead of 2.5 €/kg, compared to selling at 4.5 €/kg instead of

Fig. 9. Hydrogen average yearly production in tons.

Fig. 10. LCOH for IM and PM models in €/ton.

Fig. 11. GHG emissions as fraction of baseline system configuration.

4 €/kg. The highest rates are observed in *LE6*, in the range 2.14–2.5 €/kg. The minimal rates are observed on the other hand in the least price-sensitive *Main* scenario.

3.2. Levelized cost of hydrogen

The comparison of LCOH for the two model families in Fig. 10 demonstrates a consistent 10%–15% price difference in favor of IM,

with IMs delivering systematically lower LCOHs for the same H₂ price and scenario, for all prices and scenarios. The driving factor behind this, is that paying the RES CAPEX is ultimately overall more economical, than buying the RES energy at the PPA prices assumed in the scenarios.

An interesting result is the increase of LCOHs with hydrogen sale price, as Fig. 10 indicates. This can be attributed to the way Simplex ultimately allocates the produced hydrogen to every one-hour time slot of the energy demand time series. Time slots which are

Fig. 12. Average hydrogen energy share in the gas mixture energy mix.

“cheaper” to supply with hydrogen are prioritized, while more expensive slots are supplied last, to maximize NPV. For example, supplying hydrogen during summer noon hours—when it can be generated using CAPEX-efficient PV panels—takes precedence over supplying hydrogen at night, when RES availability is lower. This prioritization happens because of the objective function of the LP problem, which is the annualized Cash Flows of the investment; in other words, annualized income minus annualized expenditure. As expected, it becomes increasingly harder to decarbonize all energy demand, with full de-carbonization happening only in the LE6 scenario, for hydrogen sale prices over ~ 10 €/kg ($> \sim 95\%$ of the energy supplied by hydrogen, at a LCOH of ~ 4.728 €/kg) for IM and over 12 €/kg ($> \sim 95\%$ of the energy supplied by hydrogen, at a LCOH of ~ 5.724 €/kg) for PM.

3.3. Costs breakdown

While investment costs ultimately scale up with both hydrogen price and parametric scenario, PtG components’ costs as fractions of total investment costs remain constant with sale prices and scenarios. Fig. 13 shows the costs breakdown for IM and PM for the specific case of scenario LE3, when hydrogen is sold at 3.5 €/kg. This costs breakdown happens to remain more or less the same for all scenarios and prices, and it can therefore be generalized to all prices and parametric scenarios investigated in this study.

In both model families, RES production costs took up a considerable fraction of 57% – 62% of total costs. Onshore wind turbines-related costs were more than double those of PV panel-related costs in both model families. In IM in particular, RES CAPEX was four times RES Fixed OPEX.

Electrolysis costs accounted for another 37% – 41% of total costs, with electrolysis CAPEX and Fixed OPEX sharing roughly the same costs. However, this Fixed OPEX is in fact predominantly TSO fee costs, and the 6% tax on it. If green hydrogen producers were therefore exempt from these two costs, electrolysis Fixed OPEX and LCOH would be up to 63% and $\sim 4\%$ – 5% lower respectively. Other electrolysis variable OPEX, mostly water related costs, accounted for 2 – 2.3% , and AEL stack replacement every ~ 9 years, accounted for 4 – 4.3% of total costs. If AEL stack lifetimes are extended beyond 9 years however, this replacement cost would also decrease.

Hydrogen storage CAPEX and Fixed OPEX accounted for only 0.68 – 1.33% and 0.16 – 0.31% respectively, indicating that increasing hydrogen storage capacity is generally not a priority compared to increasing RES generation capacity or electrolysis capacity for instance, and it is prioritized only above hydrogen prices of ~ 10 €/kg, when installing additional RES generation adds less to the resulting NPV than increasing hydrogen storage.

3.4. NPV and ROI

A common pattern in both model families, IM and PM, as Figs. 14 and 15 suggest, is the increase of NPV and ROI with the increase of hydrogen price, as well as with parametric scenario. This means that the investment becomes increasingly profitable with hydrogen price, and as green hydrogen investment technical and economic conditions improve. However, as far as ROI is concerned, it also means that an ever smaller fraction of investment income will be invested to more H_2 production, while increasing the hydrogen price ultimately increases the profit margin.

Observing the distances between the curves of the seven scenarios in Fig. 14, it also follows that NPV is much more sensitive to the maximum allowed hydrogen volumetric blending, than to system components specific costs. For instance, the difference in NPV for price 3.5 €/kg between IM/LE2 and IM/LE3 is ~ 74 million €, whereas the difference between IM/LE3 and IM/LE4 is ~ 208 million €. This is another indication of the increase in both viability and profitability of this kind of investment with maximum allowed hydrogen blending into the NG grid.

3.5. Models comparison

Comparing the Independent and Procurement model families, IM were overall more economical when it comes to LCOH and H_2 annual production quantity (Figs. 10, 9). This can largely be attributed to the relationship between RES generation CAPEX and fixed OPEX affecting IM on the one hand, and PPA prices affecting PM on the other. For parameter scenarios other than the “Main” though, this relation was based on forecasts and assumptions. As of 2024 however, the “Main” scenario indicates that investing in RES, instead of procuring the energy from independent RES producers, is overall more economical, and leads to lower LCOHs and higher annual hydrogen productions and energy mix penetrations. Notably though, the PPA market in Greece is still rather nascent. As the number of RES producers increases in the future, PPA prices could sink faster and lower than assumed in the parametric scenarios. This could potentially bring PM LCOHs on par with IM LCOHs for the same hydrogen sale price. Moreover, PM offer the advantage of allowing a company to maintain a focused investment portfolio centered on hydrogen production, avoiding diversification and saving resources in the process.

Nevertheless, investment NPV for all H_2 prices and scenarios was higher for IM than in PM (Fig. 14), while H_2 annually produced quantities were higher at the same time (Fig. 9). On the other hand, ROI was higher for PM, indicating that this could be a better option for investors prioritizing higher ROI values over NPV (Fig. 15).

Fig. 13. Costs breakdown for IM & PM/LE3 and price 3.5 €/kg.

Fig. 14. NPV per scenario and hydrogen price.

Fig. 15. ROI per scenario and hydrogen price.

Onshore wind turbines investment or its respective PPA energy procurement in IMs is slightly prioritized compared to PV panels (Fig. 5), most probably because of a considerable proportion of the natural

gas demand occurring during the late evening and very early morning hours, especially during winter months, when solar energy is scarce. Additionally, this is due to nighttime energy demand usually being

lower than daytime demand. Also, all models point to RES generators investments generally being prioritized over hydrogen storage, with storage acquiring a considerable portion of LCOH only when additional RES capacity becomes incapable of producing more hydrogen economically, which happens for very big hydrogen sale prices (>10 €/kg). On the other hand, PV installation was slightly prioritized in PM, predominantly due to factors such as lower PPA prices for solar energy, as compared to wind turbines energy.

3.6. Limitations

Perhaps the most considerable limitation of the optimizations carried out is weather unpredictability, which is only partially reflected in the models, since the simulations carried out used $N = 3$ years of onshore wind turbines and PV panels generation data, as well as NG consumption. The reason behind this limitation is that the Simplex algorithm deployed to solve the resulting LP problems, effectively uses future RES capacity factors information or generation profiles as perfectly known parameters, in order to maximize system performance in the present time. In reality, these hourly parameters are stochastic, meaning that statistics predicted under this study, such as LCOH, NPV, ROI, are in fact the theoretically best achievable PtG system performances, under perfect weather predictability. In practice therefore, LCOH would likely be higher and NPV, ROI and average energy supplied by hydrogen as a percentage of the energy mix would be lower. Further research is required to estimate the difference between this theoretical performance, and the real-world performance of such PtG systems. In addition, research is needed to determine their optimal operation strategy, under weather and other unpredictability; in other words, under which circumstances to store what quantity of hydrogen, when to use it and how much, and at what output rate should the electrolyzer operate.

Another limitation is that the data used in the optimizations covered only the years 2014–2017. This means that the simulations carried out are also subject to yearly weather and NG consumption unpredictability, and are therefore biased. A more accurate approach would be to find confidence intervals of the predicted system and investment statistics, by running the optimizations over a broader range of years. Additionally, PtG use case performance can be changed, depending on the NG usage profiles acting behind the NG consumption time series. Modeling of multi-year techno-economic simulations of PtG use cases should ideally take into account economic phenomena such as the rise of competing technologies, changes in the demand of PtG end-products such as hydrogen, as well as regulatory and market legal frameworks changes. The environmental impact of PtG systems installations and operation should also be measured more accurately, in cost–benefit analyses.

Finally, the results of the optimizations carried out in the study were based on a linear relation between specific CAPEX and installed capacity of PtG modules, whereas in general this relationship is non-linear. This was partially addressed by considering different specific CAPEX values in the different scenarios, especially those (LE4–LE6) allowing greater overall PtG system sizes.

4. Conclusion

The objective of this study was to model, study, and compare two different investment types, aiming to partially decarbonize Athens' NG energy consumption by partially replacing the NG with green hydrogen, in a maximum-NPV manner. The hydrogen produced through the investments which included their own RES generation units to supply the electrolysis, performed overall more economically than the models procuring the required energy from third RES producers. LCOH was consistently 10%–15% more expensively produced in PMs compared to IMs, however this difference could diminish in the future, if the

PPA market in Greece becomes more widespread among consumers and producers, and PPA prices drop faster than expected.

The results importantly highlight the decarbonization vs. hydrogen sale price trade-off in the effort to substitute NG with renewable green hydrogen, when trying to maximize NPV. In all experiments, the more expensively the hydrogen was sold, the higher the sales income was, and expectedly this income was in a mathematical sense directed into the investment in more RES generation, electrolysis and storage capacity, thus more renewable hydrogen production quantities. Additionally, the same trade-off appears between LCOH and production quantity. The more H_2 is produced, the more expensive per kg it becomes. Nevertheless, this does not mean that hydrogen cannot be possibly sold cheaper, when maintaining the same hydrogen quantity, because the objective function used in this study was NPV maximization, without any GHG constraints in the LP problem. If we were to introduce GHG constraints, or if we were to minimize GHG instead of maximizing NPV, we could achieve more GHG savings for the hydrogen sale prices appearing in this study. This effect is more clearly reflected in Figs. 14(a), 14(b), which indicate that, as hydrogen sale price increases, NPV also increases, and not all monetary income goes to re-investment in hydrogen generation capacity, but it simply counts as net profit for the investor.

Full decarbonization could only be achieved at 100% maximum allowed hydrogen blending ratio, for high hydrogen sale prices of more than 10 €/kg. LCOH ranged between 2.14 and almost 5 €/kg, in accordance with other scientific literature. Almost half of it consisted of RES energy related costs, with the other half being dominated by electrolysis CAPEX and Fixed OPEX, while small parts of it were electrolyzers' stack replacement costs, and hydrogen storage CAPEX. The results showed that considerable effort is still needed in decreasing both RES energy costs and electrolysis related expenses, in order for green hydrogen production to achieve cost parity with conventional gray hydrogen, currently priced at 1–3 €/kg.

This study also assumed that no CAPEX is needed for upgrading the NG grid, in order to make it hydrogen compatible at the hydrogen injection levels considered in this study. In reality, investment for this upgrade would increase cost of moving from a fully NG-dominated gas grid, to a hydrogen dominated grid, especially during the transition period.

Hydrogen could also be produced more cost-efficiently, if it is produced by energy stemming from RES generation exclusively at times with RES surpluses. In other words, if instead of investing in all the RES generators assumed in this study, or buying the energy at prices which are the average for RES PPAs, we bought the energy only at times with electricity grid RES surpluses, then the electricity price would be much lower, for example in the range of 10–30 €/MWh. Based on the results of this study, where electricity-related costs comprise 57%–62% of total LCOH, then LCOH would be much lower compared to the results of this study. Further investigation is required to calculate LCOH, when the RES energy comes from such energy generation availability profiles and their prices.

The authors of this study hope for these outcomes to aid the decision making processes of several different actors, such as utility companies wanting to optimize their investment portfolio, policy makers' comparisons and assessments of different de-carbonization strategies, TSOs' power or NG flow optimizations, as well as energy and economics researchers.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Hercules Koutalidis: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Sotiris Pelekis:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Eugenia Skepetari:** Writing – review & editing. **Christos Ntanos:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration. **Evangelos Karakolis:** Writing – review & editing. **Ariadni Michalitsi-Psarrour:** Writing – review & editing. **Afroditi Blika:** Writing – review & editing. **Dimitris Askounis:** Funding acquisition.

Data and models availability

The data used by the models in this study and the two models developed are available as open-source GitHub repository.¹

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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¹ GitHub link: [Power-to-Gas Hydrogen investments repository](https://github.com/Power-to-Gas-Investments/Power-to-Gas-Hydrogen-investments-repository)

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